

Redox-active electrolytes as a viable approach for the one-step assembly of metal-ion capacitors

Adam Maćkowiak^a, Paweł Jeżowski^a, Yukiko Matsui^b, Masashi Ishikawa^{b,*}, Krzysztof Fic^{a,b,*}

^a Institute of Chemistry and Technical Electrochemistry, Poznan University of Technology, Berdychowo 4, Poznan 60-965, Poland

^b Department of Chemistry and Materials Engineering, Faculty of Chemistry, Materials and Bioengineering, Kansai University, 3-3-35 Yamate-cho, Suita 564-8680, Japan

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Lithium-ion capacitor
Sodium-ion capacitor
Potassium-ion capacitor
One-step preintercalation
Redox-active electrolyte
Metal-ion capacitor

ABSTRACT

The assembly of metal-ion capacitors is a very challenging task; the use of traditional metallic electrodes or sacrificial materials induces technical problems during cell assembly or affects its normal operation. Here, we report an efficient, one-step method for assembling metal-ion capacitors using redox-active electrolytes with thiocyanate-based salts. The addition of a redox-active salt compensates for the charge on the positive electrode while enabling the insertion of metal ions into the structure of the negative electrode. The proposed approach reduces assembly time and cost and results in increased specific energy compared to that from the traditional two-step assembled hybrid systems. Furthermore, we demonstrate that the proposed approach can be successfully implemented for sodium-ion and potassium-ion hybrid capacitors. Our results are supported by operando techniques and can potentially facilitate further research on metal-ion capacitors and applications of these devices.

1. Introduction

Currently, secondary batteries (especially lithium-ion batteries; LIBs) [1–3] and electrochemical capacitors (ECs) [4–7] are the two main technologies used for electrochemical energy storage. On the one hand, the storage of electrical energy in LIBs is based on slow redox reactions in the electrode bulk [8,9]; on the other hand, the energy storage in ECs is related to the formation of an electric double-layer (EDL) at the surface of electrodes [10,11]. Although LIBs can store more energy (~ 250 Wh kg^{-1}) than ECs (~ 10 Wh kg^{-1}), their power rarely exceeds 1 kW kg^{-1} , and their lifespan is limited to approximately 1000 cycles. In contrast, ECs can reach a power of 10 kW kg^{-1} and store energy continuously for millions of cycles due to the capacitive storage mechanism [12,13]. However, in recent years, a novel hybrid energy storage system that combines the features of LIBs and ECs, namely, lithium-ion capacitors (LICs) has emerged [14–17].

LIC construction is very similar to all energy storage devices; there are two electrodes, separated by a porous membrane, soaked in the electrolyte. The main difference, compared to other devices, is that the energy storage mechanism for each electrode is different. The positive electrode is most often similar to the one in ECs (porous electrodes such as activated carbon) and stores energy in the form of EDL [18], while the

negative electrode is characteristic of LIBs (for example, graphite), which undergoes continuous intercalation and deintercalation of lithium ions from its structure [19]. This internal combination of two completely different mechanisms enables the attainment of energy and power that cannot be achieved by traditional ECs and LIBs, respectively. However, to obtain a fully functional LIC, it is usually necessary to prelithiate the negative graphite electrode, and thus far, there are three available methods for successful prelithiation [20]. The first method uses metallic lithium introduced as an auxiliary electrode. When the prelithiation of graphite is performed in one cell, the intercalated graphite electrode is removed and placed in the second cell with a positive activated carbon electrode [21]. The use of metallic lithium is considered rather unsafe because it can lead to the formation of dendrites, which can further cause internal short-circuiting [22]. To avoid the mentioned issues, it is possible to incorporate lithium-rich salts into the composition of the positive activated carbon electrode and create a composite electrode [15,23,24]. During the initial polarization, the lithium salt releases lithium ions and compensates for the charge necessary for the intercalation of the negative electrode, and afterwards, the oxidized form of lithium salt is no longer electrochemically active. Nevertheless, in most cases, the oxidized salt is present in the electrode composition (forming so-called dead mass), which can significantly

* Corresponding author at: Institute of Chemistry and Technical Electrochemistry, Poznan University of Technology, Berdychowo 4, Poznan 60-965, Poland.

E-mail addresses: masaishi@kansai-u.ac.jp (M. Ishikawa), krzysztof.fic@put.poznan.pl (K. Fic).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2023.103163>

Received 20 August 2023; Received in revised form 18 December 2023; Accepted 24 December 2023

Available online 26 December 2023

2405-8297/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

decrease the overall electrochemical performance of the cell [25]; However, recent studies show that during oxidation of the lithium salt, the product can dissolve in the electrolyte [15] or be in a gaseous state [26]. Finally, the last method uses a highly concentrated electrolyte that plays the role of a lithium-ion reservoir. However, the data presented show that the drop in lithium-ion concentration is so significant that the lifespan of this device is less than 500 cycles [27].

Our study presents an original approach to the preintercalation/preinsertion of lithium-, sodium-, and potassium-ion capacitors, called metal-ion capacitors (MICs); we propose the addition of soluble redox-active salt to the electrolyte (Fig. 1).

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Redox activity of the electrolyte

Based on previous considerations, we aimed to intercalate a graphite electrode using lithium ions from the electrolyte. The current literature reports certain concepts using concentrated electrolytes, but all were unsuccessful in certain aspects [27]. The charge necessary to intercalate a negative electrode often exceeded the charge accumulated by a positive electrode. Therefore, our first approach was to balance the charge using a much larger positive electrode (10 times heavier than the negative electrode). Notably, the intercalation using only lithium ions from the electrolyte was possible if the charge of the positive electrode was properly balanced (Supplementary Fig. S1a). However, a problem developed during cycling because the large mass of the positive electrode caused the applied current to be devastating for the negative electrode (Supplementary Fig. S1b). Finally, this approach reduces the power and energy of the system [28].

To mitigate this issue, we proposed a different approach using a redox-active additive to the electrolyte. Additional redox reactions could balance the charge between the positive and negative electrodes as well as provide the necessary metal ions for preintercalation/preinsertion. For this reason, thiocyanate salts were selected as the redox-active additives because of their expected solubility in organic solvents and known redox activity in aqueous electrolytes [29]. To investigate the redox activity of SCN^- anions in an organic medium, they were studied as electrolytes in lithium-ion, sodium-ion, and potassium-ion capacitors.

Thiocyanate salts were found to be easily dissolved in organic electrolytes (carbonates) and demonstrate a redox response at ca. 3.5 V vs. metallic reference, as shown in Fig. 2a. The redox potential strongly

depended on the applied current density; thus, it was decided to use C/10 current density for the first charging process (C – theoretical capacity of graphite, 372 mAh g^{-1}). With the NaSCN system, a different solvent was used (ethylene carbonate (EC):propylene carbonate (PC) mixture, optimal for sodium-ion capacitors) [30], which reduced the operational voltage window (the signal from the electrolyte decomposition). This solvent was used due to the reaction of metallic sodium with the electrolyte $1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NaPF}_6 \text{ EC:dimethyl carbonate (DMC) containing SCN}^-$ ions (Supplementary Fig. S2a,b). Based on the cyclic voltammetry profiles, each system was characterized by two oxidation reactions of the thiocyanates. Notably, despite the presence of the SCN^- anion, which was responsible for the redox reaction, the current response differed between each system. For the sodium-ion cell, the different responses could be due to different solvent interactions [31]. However, between the lithium- and potassium-containing cells, the only difference in the cell composition was the cation, which apparently plays a significant and often underestimated role in charge storage. Another important advantage of thiocyanate salts was the irreversibility of their electrochemical reactions - reversible redox reaction could lessen the work of the positive electrode, which could affect the voltage of the entire system and, as a result, cause the energy decrease.

In practice, thiocyanate reactions were slightly reversible, as shown in Fig. 2b. The obtained capacity did not reflect the theoretical capacity (for detailed calculations for the theoretical capacity, please see the supplementary description). With each cycle, the capacity from the SCN^- reaction decreased, and it could provide the calculated value. However, the capacity obtained in the first cycle was the most important from the preinsertion process point of view. Therefore, the redox activity of thiocyanate salts fulfilled all the necessary requirements for their possible implementation in metal-ion capacitors.

2.2. Metal-ion capacitors assembled in one step

In the previous section, it was confirmed that the redox reaction occurs at well-defined electrode potentials. Next, it was necessary to determine whether the redox reaction enabled the intercalation/insertion of cations into the structure of the negative electrode without the use of a metallic electrode or sacrificial materials. For this purpose, a cell with a negative electrode (graphite) and a positive electrode (activated carbon) was assembled. Salt containing the SCN^- anion was added to the electrolyte, and the cell was charged with a C/10 current (Fig. 3a). The addition of a thiocyanate salt changed the potential slope of the response from the positive electrode, which enabled full intercalation of the

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the assembly of a traditional hybrid metal-ion capacitor and hybrid system with redox-active electrolyte.

Fig. 2. Redox activity of thiocyanate anions during the half-cell assembly for the activated carbon vs. the metallic electrode with lithium, sodium and potassium: (a) cyclic voltammetry with scan rate 0.06 mV s^{-1} (calculated from current C/10) and (b) galvanostatic charge/discharge with potential limitation with current equal to C/10.

negative electrode. For comparison, another system that did not contain thiocyanate ions was constructed. In this case, the lack of a plateau region from the response of the positive electrode caused the voltage cutoff limit to be quickly reached, which did not enable the negative electrode to even reach the second stage of intercalation. The cell was then run for cycling (Fig. 3b). The system worked very effectively; even after 1000 cycles, it maintained an efficiency above 80 % of the initial capacitance. A slight degradation of the negative electrode was observed.

The previous experiment was then repeated with the sodium-ion capacitor (Fig. 3c). In this case, the graphite was replaced with hard-carbon because of the inability of sodium to form graphite intercalation compounds. Generally, this was considered to be caused by the size mismatch between Na and the graphite interlayer spacings, but the major reason was the change in the chemical bonding between the alkali metal ions and carbon atoms [32,33]. Sodium-ion capacitors are characterized by a different mechanism of solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) formation with the insertion of sodium ions into the structure of hard-carbon. Nevertheless, the presented approach was successful since the full insertion of sodium ions into hardcarbon was obtained. In Fig. 3d, the first and 20th cycles of the system are shown. Despite the high resistance, the system retained acceptable capacitance.

Following the success of lithium- and sodium-ion systems, the technique was also tested on potassium-ion capacitors. Since potassium could react with the styrene-butadiene rubber present in the graphite electrode (Supplementary Fig. S3), the material was changed to one that did not have this additive. Fig. 3e presents the insertion of potassium ions during the initial charge of the potassium-ion capacitor. However, during cycling (Fig. 3f), problems were encountered, showing the devastating effect of potassium ions on the graphite structure. The high current forced the rapid evacuation of large potassium ions from the graphite, causing its destruction. Reducing the current (e.g., C/10) could help; however, the system would still significantly lose capacitance, and

the negative electrode potential was heading toward a zero value, i.e., the plating of metallic potassium. To improve the operation of the potassium system, a different electrolyte or negative electrode could be used; despite this, the proposed one-step assembly technique was also applicable to potassium-ion capacitors.

2.3. Comparison with traditional hybrid Li-ion capacitor

To compare hybrid one-step assembly capacitors, a traditional two-step hybrid lithium-ion capacitor was constructed. Both cells were characterized with electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (Fig. 4a). The equivalent series resistance (ESR) values were similar for both hybrid systems, as they were constructed with the same electrode materials. The response from the Stern layer on the spectra for both systems was comparable; the size of additional SCN⁻ ions did not impact the Stern layer thickness. The electric double-layer response was also similar for both hybrid systems. However, small deviations were visible for the thiocyanate-containing system, which meant that some of them were still active in the system and produced a redox response. The diffusive layer resistance (characterized by the second semicircle, Fig. 4a $\text{Re}(Z)$ ca. 16Ω) for the one-step assembly hybrid was much lower than for the traditional hybrid (21Ω) likely due to the precipitation of conductive salt on the electrode/electrolyte interphase. Therefore, the product of SCN⁻ oxidation did not negatively affect the resistance of the materials.

In the next step, the resistance was compared for both systems at a minimum (2.2 V), medium (3.2 V), and maximum (4.2 V) working voltage. The resistance curves for one-step and two-step assembly hybrids were very similar; however, for the SCN-containing system, the lower diffusive resistance enabled improved charge propagation. Additionally, it was changing with continuous working; thus, it could be concluded that certain chemical processes were ongoing in the electrolyte. In the beginning, these processes appeared beneficial for the system, but the final product of the reaction could still be a concern. The

Fig. 3. Three-electrode measurements using redox-active thiocyanates to balance the negative electrode: (a), (c), (e) first galvanostatic charging of the positive and negative electrodes using C/10 enabling preintercalation/preinsertion of cations into the structure of the negative electrode and (b), (d), (f) galvanostatic charging/discharging of the full cell; first cycle and last cycle.

equivalent distribution resistance (EDR) value for the one-step assembly hybrid was smaller, meaning that the charge was better distributed and that the maximum power of the device was higher than that for the two-step assembly system.

Comparing first charging and discharging curves for one-step and two-step assembled systems it should be noted that they are not the same (Supplementary Fig. S4). For the lithium-ion capacitor, the increased capacity of the positive electrode for the SCN-based system is notable, which affects further the energy value. In the case of the sodium-ion capacitor, there are no significant differences between the results of different construction techniques. However, in the case of a potassium-ion capacitor, the system using the two-step technique can store much more charge, which indicates that the electrolyte premetalation technique for potassium-ion capacitors should be further improved, as it is very sensitive to the given current density and potassium cations diffusion.

Subsequently, the specific power and energy of the system with the redox reactions were investigated. Fig. 5 shows the dependence of the specific power and energy of the tested systems during the first cycles of their operation. The worst energy (27 Wh kg^{-1}) properties were found in the system with a large positive electrode, which was explained earlier in the article. A hybrid potassium-ion capacitor also provided an

insufficient amount of energy (60 Wh kg^{-1}) due to the destruction of the graphite structure from large potassium ions. The sodium system was limited by hardcarbon, had a smaller capacity compared to graphite and demonstrated high energy (92 Wh kg^{-1}) and power. Moreover, the lithium-ion capacitor with redox-active electrolyte produced a very high energy (115 Wh kg^{-1}) that was comparable to lithium-ion batteries and completely outperformed the traditional hybrid capacitor (71 Wh kg^{-1}). This result was very promising because it demonstrated a lithium-ion capacitor that could offer higher power and, especially, a long life cycle.

2.4. Spectroscopic and operando GCMS investigation

To determine whether the thiocyanate anion is stable after dissolving in the electrolyte, Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were obtained (Fig. 6a). Signals from the solvents and conductive salts were observed, as well as a strong signal from the SCN^- anion at a wavelength of 2072 cm^{-1} . After confirmation of the SCN^- anions stability in the solution, a comparison of the electrolyte with SCN^- after extraction was performed. The signal from SCN decreased; however, it did not disappear completely, which confirmed that the thiocyanates were still active even after the extraction; this result agreed with electrochemical tests (Fig. 2b). A similar relationship was observed for systems with sodium

Fig. 4. Comparison of the hybrid systems assembled in one step and two steps using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy: (a) after cell assembly, (b) at minimum working voltage (2.2 V), (c) at medium working voltage (3.2 V), and (d) at maximum working voltage (4.2 V).

and potassium (Supplementary Fig. S6a,b). Proper development of the SEI was very important for the operation of the cell [34], and in the LiSCN system, the signals coming from the solvent (especially from DMC, 2965 cm^{-1} and 1605 cm^{-1}) decreased after the first charging cycle.

Raman spectra were obtained to determine the change in electrode material before and after electrochemical work (Fig. 6b and c; Supplementary Figs. S8a,b, and S9a,b). Using a microscope, small local areas could be found where a yellow precipitate appears (Supplementary Fig. S7a,b). Preliminary analysis showed that it was a complex compound of sulfur with carbon, oxygen and likely lithium. The presence of this yellow precipitate might not be beneficial for the longer cycling of the system since it could clog the pores of the activated carbon. Nevertheless, this small amount of conductive salt did not significantly affect the first cycles of the electrochemical work. To describe the precipitated compound in more detail, an analysis was performed using an X-ray diffractometer (Supplementary Figs. S10–S12). Unfortunately, the small amount of the obtained compound or its lack of crystallographic structure did not enable an accurate description of the obtained structure. Also, to extend the characterization of the system with thiocyanate anion additional experiments were performed: X-ray

Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) (Supplementary Fig. S13), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), High-Angle Annular Dark-Field Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (HAADF-STEM) and Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) (Supplementary Figs. S14–S16). Unfortunately, all performed techniques did not provide clear answer about the composition of the final product of the thiocyanate oxidation in organic medium. Probably, there are several pathways of thiocyanate oxidation. However, based on the obtained data, the final product must be still the combination of sulfur and carbon.

To investigate the SCN reaction in more detail, the system was studied using operando gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GCMS). The results presented in Fig. 7a showed the most important masses formed during the first charging of the system. The collected results were compared with those from a traditional hybrid containing no thiocyanate anions. In both cases, gases from SEI formation were visible (signals for $m/z = 24\text{--}27$); these were mostly responsible for the evolution of ethylene [35]. However, the signals obtained from the hybrid were weaker, which could mean that the SEI composition was potentially different. The main compounds that were formed during electrochemical work were ethylene (C_2H_4), carbon monosulfide (CS), carbon dioxide (CO_2), sulfur monoxide (SO), thiirene ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{S}$),

Fig. 5. Specific power and energy dependence chart of all assembled and discussed hybrid-ion capacitors (for different graph representation, please see Supplementary Fig. S5).

carbonyl sulfide (COS) and carbon disulfide (CS₂). Notably, no toxic hydrogen cyanide (HCN) was released. This result was also confirmed by performing operando GCMS for the sodium-ion capacitor (Supplementary Fig. S17a).

Based on the obtained data and previous research, a potential explanation of the reactions taking place in the system is provided. Quantitatively, the strongest signals come from $m/z = 44$ and 76 (Fig. 7b). Therefore, thiocyanate is unstable under an applied voltage, undergoes an irreversible reaction, and mainly reacts with the carbon present in the electrode material. In the first phase, the thiocyanate anion polymerizes to (SCN)₂ [29]. In the second part, the polymer is oxidized to CS [36]. During this process, elemental sulfur is also formed, deposited on the carbon, and further reacts to form CS or a substrate for the obtained precipitate. CS is an unstable compound; therefore, it reacts quickly with carbon on the surface to form CS₂ [37] or oxidizes from electrolyte decomposition products to form COS [38]. A carbon disulfate product is formed on the surface of the positive electrode made of carbon, after which it is probably also oxidized. The resulting product is noticeable on the surface of the electrode (Supplementary Fig. S7a,b).

3. Conclusion

The successful use of thiocyanate salts as a redox-active addition to the electrolyte allowed for the compensation of the charge on the positive electrode, enabling the intercalation/insertion process on the negative electrode. This provided a completely new and interesting assembly of metal-ion capacitors in just one step. First, the one-step assembled systems had lower resistance than two-step systems (16 Ω compared to 21 Ω), resulting in better diffusion and charge propagation. This was reflected in the obtained specific energy values (115 Wh kg⁻¹ compared to 71 Wh kg⁻¹). Moreover, it was shown that SCN⁻ anions underwent an irreversible reaction, which was confirmed by the signal at 2072 cm⁻¹ in the FT-IR spectra. Operando GCMS measurements indicated that the main reaction of thiocyanates was associated with the formation of CS and at a later stage, CS₂ and other oxidized species, such as COS.

One-step assembly has many advantages compared to the traditional method: lower production costs, no use of an expensive and dangerous metallic electrode, faster assembly time, and higher energy density compared to the currently used lithium-ion capacitors. Although the technique itself appears to work flawlessly, the use of thiocyanate salts has certain limitations. The complicated reaction process at high

potential causes the formation of small amounts of conductive salt on the surface of the positive electrode; noticeable volume of gases has been also observed. Nevertheless, these issues do not discredit the concept, as they can be easily solved at the device processing level (e.g., primary gas evacuation); of course, changing the redox additive can potentially solve these issues too; however, this is a challenging task for future research.

Proposed approach could close the gap between lithium-ion batteries and metal-ion capacitors. We believe that this concept could revolutionize the metal-ion capacitor market and facilitate the development of sustainable energy storage devices.

4. Experimental section

Electrolyte: Salts: lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF₆), potassium hexafluorophosphate (KPF₆), sodium perchlorate (NaClO₄), lithium thiocyanate hydrate (LiSCN xH₂O), sodium thiocyanate (NaSCN) and potassium thiocyanate (KSCN) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck). Before use, all salts were dried under a vacuum at 120°C for one week to remove water contamination. Lithium thiocyanate hydrate salt was predried at 100°C using a liquid nitrogen cold trap to remove excess water. Anhydrous solvents: ethylene carbonate (EC), propylene carbonate (PC), and dimethyl carbonate (DMC) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck). The electrolyte preparation for lithium cell investigations consisted of preparing a 1 molar solution of LiPF₆ in ethylene carbonate and dimethyl carbonate mixed in a volumetric ratio of 1:1 with an addition of a calculated amount of dissolved LiSCN salt. The same approach was used for the potassium cells, but instead of LiPF₆ and LiSCN, KPF₆ and KSCN salts were used. The electrolyte preparation for sodium investigations consisted of preparing a 1 molar solution of NaClO₄ in ethylene carbonate and propylene carbonate mixed in a volumetric ratio of 1:1 with an addition of a calculated amount of NaSCN salt. The mass of thiocyanate salts added to each electrolyte was determined by the mass of each negative electrode and its theoretical capacity (Supplementary description). Then, 600 μ L of the electrolytes received were added to soak the separators during electrochemical cell preparation. All reagents were stored in the MBraun glovebox, which ensured inert environmental conditions. The conductivity values of the electrolytes obtained are shown in Supplementary Information Fig. S19. The conductivity measurement was performed at 25°C using a 2-electrode Swagelok system with a spacer, and the impedance spectroscopy method was used to calculate the conductivity from the resistance.

Electrode material: The negative electrode of the hybrid Li-ion capacitor was made of copper foil covered with a mixture of graphite, styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR), carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) and carbon black (total thickness = 57 μ m) provided by the MTI corporation (Supplementary Fig. S20a). The negative electrode of the hybrid Na-ion capacitor was a laboratory-prepared electrode made of copper foil coated with a mixture of hardcarbon (Carbotron P, Kureha), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and carbon black (total thickness = 93 μ m) (Supplementary Fig. S20b). The negative electrode of the hybrid K-ion capacitor was graphite mixed with CMC and coated on copper foil (total thickness = 100 μ m) and was provided by Customcells® (Supplementary Fig. S20c). The positive electrode of all metal-ion capacitors was a self-standing electrode made of Kuraray YP80F (80 %), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) (10 %) and carbon black C65 (10 %) (total thickness = 114 μ m). The microtextural characteristics of the positive electrode were determined by using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) isotherm method (77 K) with N₂ as an adsorbate (ASAP 2460, Micromeritics, USA). 1558 m² g⁻¹ was the surface area of the positive electrode [6]. Before the adsorption/desorption steps, samples were flushed at 350°C for 12 h under continuous helium flow and further degassed at 25°C for 5 h (vacuum). The reference electrodes were made from metallic lithium, sodium and potassium (all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich). During half-cell measurements, the counter electrode and reference electrode were shaped as metallic discs (d = 16 mm).

Cell assembly: First, round electrodes (d = 16 mm, A = 2 cm²) were

Fig. 6. (a) FT-IR spectra of the electrolyte with thiocyanate anions and the electrolyte after extraction in a lithium-ion capacitor assembled using a one-step approach; Raman spectra of the (b) positive electrode and (c) negative electrodes before and after lithium-ion capacitor electrochemical work (1000 cycles).

cut from positive and negative electrode materials using EL-Cut provided by EL-CELL®. The active mass ratio of the electrodes was approximately 1:1. Then, the electrolyte was prepared. Before each cell was assembled, the electrolyte was freshly prepared. After, the positive and negative electrodes were placed in the ECC-REF electrochemical cell (provided by EL-CELL®) and separated using two glass fibre discs ($d = 18$ mm, GF/D, Whatman®) soaked with 600 μ L of electrolyte. The reference electrode was inserted as metal pieces in the reference pinhole using an ECC loader (provided by EL-CELL®). All cells were prepared in a glovebox (MBraun) to ensure negligible amounts of water and oxygen (<0.1 ppm). For a detailed specification of cell assembly, see the description in Supplementary Information.

Spectroscopic investigation: Infrared spectra of the electrolyte were obtained using an infrared spectrometer (Nicolet™ iS5 FT-IR) in the 1000-3500 cm^{-1} wavenumber range. Electrode materials were tested before and after electrochemical work with a Raman DXR microscope (Thermo Fischer Scientific). Special closed cuvettes with Kapton tape were used to prevent precipitation from oxidation. The laser power (DXR 532 nm) was 0.5 to 5 mW, and the exposure time was 8×20 s using

a pinhole of 50 μ m. X-ray diffractograms were obtained from a BRUKER D8 Advanced apparatus equipped with a Johansson monochromator using Cu K α radiation (Cu K α , $\lambda = 1.5406$ Å) and a LynxEye silicon strip detector. The measurement angle was between 5 and 100 2θ deg. Gas chromatography with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis was conducted using EVOQ GC-TQ™ MS, Bruker. The apparatus was connected to PAT-Cell-Gas made by EL-CELL®. The electrochemical cell was inserted into the thermostatic chamber (25°C). The temperature of the injector was 190°C, the column was 170°C and the mass spectrometer was 220°C.

Electrochemical investigation: Electrochemical measurements were performed in the ECC-Ref and PAT-Cell-Gas (in the case of GCMS measurement) systems provided by the EL-CELL®. The reference metallic lithium pin was introduced to ECC-Ref by using ECC-Load. Electrochemical measurements (cyclic voltammetry, galvanostatic charge/discharge with potential limitations, and impedance spectroscopy) were performed via a multichannel galvanostat/potentiostat (VMP-3 BioLogic®). Temperature control was provided by a thermostatic chamber.

Fig. 7. (a) Comparison of operando GCMS results of lithium-ion capacitors assembled using a one-step (darker line) and a two-step (lighter line) approach (b) only masses used for the main SCN^- reaction in one-step approach.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Adam Maćkowiak: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Paweł Jeżowski:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Yukiko Matsui:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Masashi Ishikawa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Krzysztof Fic:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Software.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the European Research Council within the Starting Grant project (GA 759603) under European

Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. KF would like to acknowledge the funding received from the Polish Ministry for Science and Higher Education for a research stay at Kansai University (JP) (contract No. 1718/1/MOB/V/2018/0). PJ would also like to acknowledge the Foundation for Polish Science and the START 2019 programme.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.enstm.2023.103163](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enstm.2023.103163).

References

- [1] C. Sun, X. Zhang, C. Li, K. Wang, X. Sun, Y. Ma, Fast charging of energy-dense lithium-ion batteries, *Energy Storage Mater.* 32 (2020) 497–516.
- [2] J.T. Frith, M.J. Lacey, U. Ulissi, A non-academic perspective on the future of lithium-based batteries, *Nat. Commun.* 14 (2023) 420.
- [3] I. Konuma, D. Goonetilleke, N. Sharma, T. Miyuki, S. Hiroi, K. Ohara, Y. Yamakawa, Y. Morino, H.B. Rajendra, T. Ishigaki, N. Yabuuchi, A near dimensionally invariable high-capacity positive electrode material, *Nat. Mater.* 22 (2023) 225–234.
- [4] P. Simon, Y. Gogotsi, Perspectives for electrochemical capacitors and related devices, *Nat. Mater.* 19 (2020) 1151–1163.
- [5] J.B. Goodenough, K.S. Park, The Li-ion rechargeable battery: a perspective, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (2013) 1167–1176.
- [6] K. Fic, A. Platek, J. Piwek, E. Frackowiak, Sustainable materials for electrochemical capacitors, *Mater. Today* 21 (2018) 437–454.
- [7] S.E.M. Pourhosseini, A. Bothe, A. Balducci, F. Beguin, P. Ratajczak, Strategy to assess the carbon electrode modifications associated with the high voltage ageing of electrochemical capacitors in organic electrolyte, *Energy Storage Mater.* 38 (2021) 17–19.
- [8] J.W. Choi, D. Aurbach, Promise and reality of post-lithium-ion batteries with high energy densities, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* 1 (2016) 16013.

- [9] J.M. Tarascon, Material science as a cornerstone driving battery research, *Nat. Mater.* 21 (2022) 979–982.
- [10] P. Simon, Y. Gogotsi, Materials for electrochemical capacitors, *Nat. Mater.* 7 (2008) 845–854.
- [11] M. Salanne, B. Rotenberg, K. Naoi, K. Kaneko, P.L. Taberna, C.P. Grey, B. Dunn, P. Simon, Efficient storage mechanisms for building better supercapacitors, *Nat. Energy* 1 (2016) 16070.
- [12] W. Cao, J. Zhang, H. Li, Batteries with high theoretical energy densities, *Energy Storage Mater.* 26 (2020) 46.
- [13] J. Zhao, A.F. Burke, Electrochemical capacitors: performance metrics and evaluation by testing and analysis, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (2021) 2002192.
- [14] M.R. Lukatskaya, B. Dunn, Y. Gogotsi, Multidimensional materials and device architectures for future hybrid energy storage, *Nat. Commun.* 7 (2016) 12647.
- [15] P. Jeżowski, O. Crosnier, E. Deunf, P. Poizat, F. Béguin, T. Brousse, Safe and recyclable lithium-ion capacitors using sacrificial organic lithium salt, *Nat. Mater.* 17 (2018) 167–173.
- [16] X. Yang, F. Cheng, O. Ka, L. Wen, X. Gu, W. Hou, W. Lu, L. Dai, High-voltage lithium-ion capacitors enabled by a multifunctional phosphite electrolyte additive, *Energy Storage Mater.* 46 (2022) 431–442.
- [17] M. Soltani, S.H. Beheshti, A comprehensive review of lithium ion capacitor: development, modelling, thermal management and applications, *J. Energy Storage* 34 (2021) 102019.
- [18] K. Kato, M.T.F. Rodrigues, G. Babu, P.M. Ajayan, Revealing anion chemistry above 3V in Li-ion capacitors, *Electrochim. Acta* 324 (2019) 134871.
- [19] N. Ogiwara, M. Hasegawa, H. Kumagai, R. Mikita, N. Nagasako, Heterogeneous intercalated metal-organic framework active materials for fast-charging non-aqueous Li-ion capacitors, *Nat. Commun.* 14 (2023) 1472.
- [20] L. Jin, C. Shen, A. Shellikeri, Q. Wu, J. Zheng, P. Andrei, J.G. Zhang, J.P. Zheng, Progress and perspectives on pre-lithiation technologies for lithium ion capacitors, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 13 (2020) 2341–2362.
- [21] T. Aida, K. Yamada, M. Morita, An advanced hybrid electrochemical capacitor that uses a wide potential range at the positive electrode, *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.* 9 (2006) A534.
- [22] W. Li, H. Yao, K. Yan, G. Zheng, Z. Liang, Y.M. Chiang, Y. Cui, The synergetic effect of lithium polysulfide and lithium nitrate to prevent lithium dendrite growth, *Nat. Commun.* 6 (2015) 7436.
- [23] X. Wang, L. Liu, Z. Niu, Carbon-based materials for lithium-ion capacitors, *Mater. Chem. Front.* 3 (2019) 1265–1279.
- [24] P. Jeżowski, K. Fic, O. Crosnier, T. Brousse, F. Béguin, Lithium rhenium(VII) oxide as a novel material for graphite pre-lithiation in high performance lithium-ion capacitors, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 4 (2016) 12609–12615.
- [25] P. Jeżowski, K. Fic, O. Crosnier, T. Brousse, F. Béguin, Use of sacrificial lithium nickel oxide for loading graphitic anode in Li-ion capacitors, *Electrochim. Acta* 206 (2016) 440–445.
- [26] P. Jeżowski, A. Chojnacka, X. Pan, F. Béguin, Sodium amide as a “zero dead mass” sacrificial material for the pre-sodiation of the negative electrode in sodium-ion capacitors, *Electrochim. Acta* 375 (2021) 137980.
- [27] C. Decaux, G. Lota, E. Raymundo-Piñero, E. Frackowiak, F. Béguin, Electrochemical performance of a hybrid lithium-ion capacitor with a graphite anode preloaded from lithium bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide-based electrolyte, *Electrochim. Acta* 86 (2012) 282–286.
- [28] V. Khomenko, E. Raymundo-Piñero, F. Béguin, High-energy density graphite/AC capacitor in organic electrolyte, *J. Power Sources* 177 (2008) 643–651.
- [29] B. Gorska, P. Bujewska, K. Fic, Thiocyanates as attractive redox-active electrolytes for high-energy and environmentally-friendly electrochemical capacitors, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 19 (2017) 7923–7935.
- [30] A. Ponrouch, E. Marchante, M. Courty, J.-M. Tarascon, M.R. Palacín, In search of an optimized electrolyte for Na-ion batteries, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 8572–8583.
- [31] X. Pan, A. Chojnacka, P. Jeżowski, F. Béguin, Na₂S sacrificial cathodic material for high performance sodium-ion capacitors, *Electrochim. Acta* 318 (2019) 471–478.
- [32] H. Moriwake, A. Kuwabara, C.A.J. Fisher, Y. Ikuhara, Why is sodium-intercalated graphite unstable? *RSC Adv.* 7 (2017) 3655–36554.
- [33] J.Y. Hwang, S.T. Myung, Y.K. Sun, Sodium-ion batteries: present and future, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 46 (2017) 3529–3614.
- [34] J.E.N. Swallow, M.W. Fraser, N.J.H. Kneusels, J.F. Charlton, C.G. Sole, C.M. E. Phelan, E. Björklund, P. Bencok, C. Escudero, V. Pérez-Dieste, C.P. Grey, R. J. Nicholls, R.S. Weatherup, Revealing solid electrolyte interphase formation through interface-sensitive Operando X-ray absorption spectroscopy, *Nat. Commun.* 13 (2022) 6070.
- [35] T. Liu, L. Lin, X. Bi, L. Tian, K. Yang, J. Liu, M. Li, Z. Chen, J. Lu, K. Amine, K. Xu, F. Pan, In situ quantification of interphasial chemistry in Li-ion battery, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 14 (2019) 50–56.
- [36] T.S. Miller, A. d'Aleo, T. Suter, A.E. Aliev, A. Sella, P.F. McMillan, Pharaoh's serpents: new insights into a classic carbon nitride material, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* 643 (2017) 1572–1580.
- [37] E.K. Moltzen, K.J. Klabunde, A. Senning, Carbon monosulfide: a review, *Chem. Rev.* 88 (1988) 391–406.
- [38] M. Abián, M. Cebrián, Á. Millera, R. Bilbao, M.U. Alzueta, CS₂ and COS conversion under different combustion conditions, *Combust. Flame* 162 (2015) 2119–2127.